

INTEGRATIVE APPROACH AS A BASIS FOR FORMING COMPETENCE

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New generation standards based on a competency-based approach are entering the system of higher professional education. In this regard, it should be emphasized that even a thorough study of the very structure of professional competence and the competencies included in it, which has been actively carried out recently by many specialists, does not in itself allow us to answer the most important question: how exactly, with the help of what mechanisms, to form this competence? Competence as a systemic new formation cannot arise instantly.

Long-term work is required not only by the teacher, but also by the student himself, connected not only with the application of knowledge in practice, but with overcoming external and internal barriers, with awareness of his own characteristics both as an individual and as a subject of professional activity. It can be said that the formation of a specialist's professional competence is, first of all, a subjective appropriation, the interiorization of subject knowledge, its transition into personal knowledge, "integrated" into professional thinking.

Continuity, succession, systematicity and integration at all levels of education are important for the implementation of such a strategy. At the same time, the solution to the problem of systematization and integration of knowledge depends to a significant extent on the efforts of the student himself. The project method, polytechnicism in teaching, the connection of teaching with production and productive work, the implementation of interdisciplinary connections, the relationship between general and vocational education, the consolidation of didactic units, the technology of modular teaching - all these are examples of some significant directions for the implementation of the idea of integration in domestic pedagogical practice.

V.S. Bezrukova, I.D. Zverev, K.Yu. Kolesina, N.Yu. Kustov, V.N. Maksimova, N.K. Chapaev and other researchers identify various types, characteristics, levels and indicators of integration. The problem of integration in vocational education was developed in detail by A.P. Belyaeva, M.N. Berulava, L.A. Volovich, V.V. Kondratyev, A.A. Kirsanov, A.A. Kupriyanov, M.I. Makhmutov, G.V. Mukhametzyanova, A.M. Novikov, Z.S. Sazonova, Yu.S. Tyunnikov and others (see: [1–4]).

In a broad sense, integration is usually understood as the process of uniting disunited components into a new whole. In the case of pedagogical integration, these may be

new qualities, connections and functions of the pedagogical system and, as a consequence, new competencies formed in the process of professional training within the framework of this system.

Although in modern pedagogical research the “integrative approach” is often mentioned as being in parallel with the “competency-based” approach, this is hardly correct. Rather, it can be assumed that the integrative approach in its various manifestations and levels of application (integration of science, education and production, integration of education at its various levels, integration of the educational content of individual disciplines and much more) is a means of developing professional competence. Competencies can be considered as new formations that constitute the quintessence of professional thinking and individual style of professional activity. This applies primarily to competencies formed during the study of psychological and pedagogical disciplines.

In the system of continuous professional education in a technical university, they are the basis of the psychological and pedagogical component of the professional competence of a specialist. Psychological and pedagogical training is one of the most important factors in the formation of three blocks of competencies: social-personal, personal-activity and cognitive.

Social and personal competencies allow for interaction with people and management in subsequent professional activities. Personal and activity competencies make it possible to gain self-knowledge, understand one's strengths and weaknesses, find effective individual styles of professional activity, and professional self-development. Cognitive competencies are necessary for successful work with information and self-education.

The block of social and personal competencies of a specialist includes the following components: knowledge about a person as a subject of communication, about the patterns of interaction between people in professional groups and teams; skills, abilities and experience of interacting with people in various situations, readiness to take leadership in solving complex production and social problems; reflection of one's own characteristics as a subject of communication and professional interaction; communicative (allowing for effective exchange of information), perceptual (allowing for understanding people and developing successful tactics of interaction with them) and interactive (allowing for organizing joint professional activities) abilities and personal qualities; basics of individual style of professional communication (use of the strengths of the specialist); experience of communication when performing various professional roles.

The block of personal-activity competencies includes such components as: knowledge of the essence and structure of personality and activity; skills and experience of self-knowledge that allow one to recognize oneself as a subject of professional activity, possessing both individual characteristics and the most important professionally significant qualities; a focus on self-realization; understanding the essence of the processes of self-education and self-education, which provide the opportunity for professional growth; the formation of an individual style of educational and professional activity; other qualities that ensure professional self-development.

The following components can be identified in the block of cognitive competencies: understanding the essence and structure of the cognitive sphere and its features, manifested both in educational and professional activities; skills, experience of working with professionally significant information; ability to self-learn; individual style of thinking and professional activity. The development of the described competencies in a technical university is possible within the framework of continuous psychological and pedagogical training based on an integrative approach.

LITERATURE

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